

ON-LINE AND OFF-LINE SIMULATION OF DC MOTOR SYSTEM CONTROLLED BY PID AND FUZZY CONTROLLERS

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Abstract

Real-time Simulation is a simulation that is carried out with discrete time step which involves the input, output systems and modeling of hardware and software components. In this paper the analysis of real time simulation of a DC motor is done using Arduino DUE microcontroller by implementing the hardware-in-loop architecture to the mathematical model. The variations in the system parameters can be exactly analysed without the presence of the physical system. The real time simulation plays vital role in equipment commissioning and testing by providing a test bench or a test case to the model. The scope of this work includes the comparison of offline and online simulations of fuzzy logic and PID controlled DC motor system.

Index Terms:Real Time Simulation (RTS), Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC), Proportional Integral Derivative Controller (PID), Hardware-in-loop Architecture (HIL)

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays before implementing an actual physical system, its simulation models are executed, and its characteristics are obtained. Simulation is a tool for designing, operating and understanding complex systems in power systems and power electronics. Broadly simulation can be of two types off-line and Real-time Simulation. Off-line simulation uses a digital computer and Real-time Simulation uses a dedicated high speed digital processing hardware (Arduino DUE board & C2000 Delfino F28377S). The most widely used simulation model is the offline simulation, in which the time period is a variable one. It has two major drawbacks such as the computation time is longer than the fixed time step (over run error) and the computation time is shorter than the fixed time step. The result thus obtained through offline simulation is inaccurate. In order to overcome this problem Real-time Simulation (online simulation) can be used. Real-time simulation refers to a computer model of a physical system that can execute at the same rate as actual clock time (i.e.) the computer model runs with the same time period of the actual physical system. For e.g. in some places around the world the process of deep sea oil drilling is effected through the real time simulation technique.

Real time digital simulation concepts and are used for analysis, design of systems and commissioning of electrical apparatus. It demonstrates the general framework for the software, hardware, I/O system modeling of any electrical system and also gives the classification of Real time systems [1]. The offline simulation fails to follow the real time clock because of the process variations delays, noise, mode of operation and saturation on the control system. So in order to avoid the problems faced in offline simulation, the real-time simulation is used [11,13]

Motors are generally used in industries to carry out mechanical work. The selection of the motor for an industrial application depends on its speed torque-characteristics. The wireless monitoring the conditions and efficiency of three phase induction motor which

is done by Real time system method [4]. A DC motor is a machine that provides mechanical energy by circulation of current in a coil .The DC motor has an advantage of operating at high torque and wide speed thus the controllability of DC motors easy by the use of controllers like fuzzy, PID,ANN etc [3]. PID is the one that controls by comparing the value obtained with the set point value and is mainly used in position control study [7], where as fuzzy controls the output based on rules formulated from the knowledge-base [6,16].

The Real-time Simulation enabled by arduino microcontroller minimizes the design process, helps in rapid prototyping at the expense of minimal design cost [8]

As the design of controllers is done with ease by using Real-time Simulation. So the investigation of real time simulated DC motor controlled by different controllers is necessary

2 DISCUSSION ON OFFLINE SIMULATION AND REAL-TIME SIMULATION

2.1 Offline Simulation

Off-line simulation is a one that is generally carried out with standard software packages, allows flexibility in analyzing a wide variety of components and systems. For digital simulation it is assumed that a simulation with discrete-time and constant step duration is performed. During discrete-time simulation, time moves forward in steps of equal duration. This is commonly known as fixed time-step simulation. It is seen that there is also variable time-step simulations such techniques are used for solving high frequency dynamics and non-linear systems. To solve mathematical functions and equations at a given time-step, each variable or system state is solved successively as a function of variables and states at the end of the proceeding time-step. During a discrete time simulation, the amount of real time required to compute all equations and functions representing a system during a given time-step is shorter or longer than the duration of the simulation time step as shown in Fig 1.

(a) & Fig1. (b) In Fig 1. (a) The computing time is shorter than the fixed time-step (also referred to as accelerated simulation) while in Fig1. (b) The computing time is longer. These two situations are referred to as offline simulation. In both cases, the moment at which a result becomes available is irrelevant.

Fig.1. (a) Offline Simulation-Faster than fixed time-step (b) Offline Simulation-Slower than fixed time step

Typically, when performing offline simulation, the objective is to obtain results as fast as possible. The system solving speed depends on available computation power and the systems mathematical model complexity.

2.2 Real-time-simulation

In the real-time simulation, the accuracy of computations not only depends upon precise dynamic representation of the system, but also on the length of time used to produce results as shown in Fig1 (c). For a real-time simulation to be accepted, the real-time simulator used must accurately produce the internal variables and outputs of the simulation within the same length of time that its physical counterpart would, or it should rather be a little shorter than the Real- time clock. This accounts for delays caused due to I/O interactions thus For a given time-step, any idle-time preceding or following simulator operations is lost; as opposed to accelerated simulation, where idle time is used to compute the equations at the next time-step. Real-time digital simulation is based on discrete time-steps where the simulator solves model equations successively. Proper time-step duration must be determined to accurately represent system frequency response upto the fastest transient of interest. Simulation results can be validated when the simulator achieves real-time without overruns. For each time- step, the simulator executes the same series of tasks.

- Read inputs and generate outputs.
- Solve model equations.
- Exchange results with other simulation nodes.
- Wait for the start of the next step.

Fig.1. (c) Real Time Simulation-Synchronized

3 DC MOTOR AND ITS DC MOTOR EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT

Almost every mechanical movement around us is accomplished by an electric motor. Electric machines are a means of converting energy. Motors take electrical energy and produce mechanical energy. Electric motors are broadly classified into two different categories: DC (Direct Current) and AC (Alternating Current). In most cases, regardless of type, electric motors consist of a stator (stationary field) and a rotor (the rotating field or armature) and operate through the interaction of magnetic flux and electric current to produce rotational speed and torque.

Fig.2. Equivalent circuit for DC Motor

3.1 Need for speed control of DC motors

All DC motors will lose speed as they are loaded and increase in speed when they are unloaded, in a linear fashion, according to their speed/torque gradient. For applications where a specific speed is required, with an unknown load (so a final speed cannot be calculated), or a fluctuating load (conveyor belt, pump, grinding tool, reel / converter, Cam) a controller is a must, which can be used to modify the behavior of this system so as it behaves in a specific desirable way over a time.

$$E_a(t) = R_a i_a + L_a di_a/dt + e_b \quad (1)$$

$$E_a(t) = R_a i_a + L_a di_a/dt + K_b w(t) \quad (2)$$

For normal operation, the developed torque must be equal to the load torque plus the friction and inertia.

$$T_m(t) = j_m d_w(t)/dt + B_m w(t) + T_L \quad (3)$$

$T_m(t)$ equal to $K_t I_a$ and $T_L = 0$ yields

$$K_T I_a(t) = j_m d_w(t)/dt + B_m w(t) \quad (4)$$

Taking the Laplace transform for eqn(2) and (4) yields

$$E_a(s) = R_a(s)I_a(s) + L_a I_a(s)s + K_b w(s) \quad (5)$$

$$K_T I_a(s) = J_m w(s)s + B_m W(s) \quad (6)$$

$$I_a(s) = J_m w(s)s + B_m W(s)/K_T \quad (7)$$

substitute in eqn(5)

$$E_a(s) = w(s)[(R_a J_m s + R_a B_m) + (L_a J_m s^2 + L_a B_m(s)) + K_b K_T]/K_T \quad (8)$$

So the relationship between rotor shaft speed and applied armature voltage is represented by the transfer function

$$W(s)/E_a(s) = K_T/L_a J_m s^2 + (R_a J_m + L_a B_m)s + R_a B_m + K_b K_T \quad (9)$$

Thus for the controller to regulate the speed response the voltage of the system must vary accordingly.

Table 1. Function of DC motor

Functions	Abbreviated form	Units
E_a	Armature voltage	V
I_a	Armature current	A
R_a	Resistance	Ohms(Ω)
L_a	Inductance	H
e_b	Back emf	V
T_m & T_L	Motor torque and Load torque	Nm
J	Rotor inertia	Kg.m
ω	Angular speed	Rad.s^{-1}
B	Viscous friction coefficient	Nms.rad^{-1}

Specification of Dc Motor under study

Table 1. Specification of DC motor

Parameter of DC motor	Value
Armature resistance(R_a)	1Ω
Armature inductance(L_a)	0.5H
Inertia (J)	0.01kgm^2
Damping (B)	0.1Nms/rad

4 COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FLC AND PID

4.1 PID controller

A proportionalintegralderivative controller (PID controller) is a control loop feedback mechanism. As the name suggests, PID algorithm consists of three basic coefficients: proportional, integral and derivative which are varied to get optimal response.

Fig.3. Block diagram of PID controller

The entire idea of this algorithm revolves around manipulating the error. The error as is evident is the difference between the process, variable and the set point.

$$\text{ERROR} = \text{PV} - \text{SP}$$

The proportional calculates the error at a instant, the integral accumulates the error, and the derivative keeps track of the differential error. The effect of the derivative is to counteract the overshoot caused by P and I quantities in the controller. When the error is large, the P and I controller will give the controller output. This controller response will make the error to change quickly, which in turn causes the derivative to counteract the P and I quantities in the controller.

4.2 Fuzzy logic controller (FLC)

These controllers are used for decision making process, which are based on the theory of approximate reasoning and it is a trial and error method which enables linguistic statements to be treated mathematically. Fuzzy rely on human thinking. Thus fuzzy logic is intuitive and qualitative rather than quantitative and systematic. It has only two inputs error and differential error which gives the output (based on the linguistic statements obtained from comparison of two inputs). Every fuzzy system is composed of four principal blocks (Fig 4.)

- Knowledge base (rules and parameters for membership functions)
- Decision unit (inference operations on the rules)
- Fuzzication interface (transformation of the crisp inputs into degrees of match with linguistic variables)
- Defuzzication interface (transformation of the fuzzy result of the inference into a crisp output)

Fig 4. General structure of fuzzy system

5 SIMULATION MODEL OF DC MOTOR USING PID AND FLC CONTROLLERS

Fig 5 (a). Simulation model for DC motor with PID Controller

Fig 5 (a). Simulation model for DC motor with FLC controller

5.1 Offline-simulation observations and inferences

Fig 6 (a). varying speed of DC motor speed at no-load

Fig 6 (b). varying speed of DC motor speed at full-load

Initially reference speed is 500 RPM and PID output starts from 0 and rises to 450 RPM (90% of ref value) at a time of 1.09 sec(rise time),the output reaches a overshoot is 9.4% and settles at a time period of 2.67 sec(settling time).After 7 sec the reference speed is 1000 RPM the PID output rises from 500 RPM to 900 RPM(90%

of ref value) at a time of 0.96 sec(rise time),the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 4.7% and settles at a time of 2.67% (settling time).After 14 sec the reference speed is 1500 RPM the PID output rises from 1000 RPM to 1350 RPM at a time of 0.85 sec(rise time),the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 3.1% and settles at a time of 2.67%(settling time) and the response ends at a time of 20 sec(run time) as shown in fig 6 (a).

Initially reference speed is 500 RPM and FLC output starts from 0 and rises to 450 RPM (90% of ref value)at a time of 0.22 sec(rise time), the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 9.8% and settles at a speed of 492 RPM with an error of 8 RPM(with the reference)at a time of 0.46 sec (settling time). After 7 sec the reference speed is 1000 RPM and the FLC output rises from 492 RPM to 900 RPM(90% of ref value) at a time of 0.25 sec(rise time) ,the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 0.7% and settles at value of 987 RPM with an error of 13 RPM(with the reference)at a time of 0.46(settling time).After 14 sec the reference speed is 1500 RPM and the FLC output rises from 987 RPM to 1350 RPM(90% of ref value) at a time of 0.34 sec(rise time),the output reaches a maximum undershoot of 1.13% and settles at speed of 1484RPM with an error of 14RPM(with the reference)at a time of 0.76 sec and the response ends at a time of 20 sec(run time) as shown in fig 6 (a).

Initially when the reference Initially reference speed is 500 RPM and PID output starts from negative value of -120 and rises to 450 RPM (90% of ref value) at a time of 1.15 sec(rise time),the output reaches a overshoot is 12% and settles at a time period of 2.7 sec(settling time).After 7 sec the reference speed is 1000 RPM the PID output rises from 500 RPM to 900 RPM(90% of ref value) at a time of 1.05 sec(rise time),the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 6% and settles at a time of 3% (settling time).After 14 sec the reference speed is 1500 RPM the PID output rises from 1000 RPM to 1350 RPM at a time of 0.85 sec(rise time),the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 3.13% and settles at a time of 2.7%(settling time) and the response ends at a time of 20 sec (run time) as shown in fig 6 (b).

Initially reference speed is 500 RPM and FLC output starts

from 0 and rises to 450 RPM (90% of ref value) at a time of 0.264 sec (rise time), the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 7% and settles at a speed of 487 RPM with an error of 10 RPM (with the reference) at a time of 0.48 sec (settling time). After 7 sec the reference speed is 1000 RPM and the FLC output rises from 490 RPM to 900 RPM (90% of ref value) at a time of 0.36 sec (rise time), the output reaches a maximum overshoot of 0.7% and settles at value of 985 RPM with an error of 15 RPM (with the reference) at a time of 0.6 (settling time). After 14 sec the reference speed is 1500 RPM and the FLC output rises from 987 RPM to 1320 RPM (88% of final value) and settles at this speed at time of 1.05 sec with a speed error of 180 RPM and the response ends at time of 20 sec (run time) as shown in fig 6 (b).

Table 3. Variation of speed of DC motor at constant load of no-load and full-load

SPEED	PARAMETERS MEASURED	NO LOAD		FULL LOAD	
		PID	FLC	PID	FLC
500 RPM	overshoot time	1.09	0.22	1.15	0.264
	settling time	2.67	0.46	2.7	0.48
	maximum overshoot & drop	9.4% overshoot	9.8% overshoot	12% overshoot	7% overshoot
1000 RPM	overshoot time	0.96	0.25	1.05	0.36
	settling time	2.67	0.46	3	0.6
	maximum overshoot & drop	4.7% overshoot	0.7% overshoot	6% overshoot	1.7% drop
1500 RPM	overshoot time	0.85	0.34	0.85	Does not reach 90% of its final value
	settling time	2.67	0.76	2.7	Settles at 1320 RPM at 1.05 sec
	maximum overshoot & drop	3.1% overshoot	1.13% drop	3.13% overshoot	12% drop

From the comparison made from table 3 it is observed that the rise time, settling time are lesser for FLC than that for PID it is also found that the rise time, settling time also varies with the application of load. This implies that the FLC responds quickly to the variations in the system, but at full load and 1500 speed FLC output is 1320 RPM (i.e.) 180 RPM lesser when compared with the reference of 1500 RPM this error value can be greatly minimized by adding additional rules to the rulebase that decides the output

of an FLC as shown in table 3.

Fig 7

(a). Varying load for a constant speed of 500 RPM (b). Varying load for a constant speed of 1000 RPM

The reference speed is kept constant at 500 RPM the output speed of PID reaches 450 RPM (90% of reference value) at a time of 1.08 sec (rise time), its maximum overshoot is 9.4% and the response settles at a time of 4.31 sec (settling time). After 7 sec a load TL1 with initial value of 0 and final value of 0.01 is applied, due to which there is a sudden drop by 30% and it settles at a time of 4.45 sec (settling time). After 14 sec a TL2 of initial and final value of 0 and -0.01 respectively is added along with TL1 due to which there is a drop by 29.6% and it settles at a time of 4.45 sec (settling time) and the response ends at a time of 20 sec (run time) as shown in fig 7 (a).

The reference speed is kept constant at 500 RPM the output speed of FLC reaches 450 RPM (90% of reference value) at a time of 0.22 sec (rise time), its maximum overshoot is 9.6% and the response settles at a time of 0.4 sec (settling time). After 7 sec a load TL1 with initial value of 0 and final value of 0.01 is applied, due to which there is a sudden drop by 11.61% and it settles at a time of 0.4 sec (settling time). After 14 sec a TL2 of initial and final value of 0 and -0.01 respectively is added along with TL1 due to which there is a drop by 19.8% and it settles at a time of 0.4 sec (settling time) and the response ends at a time of 20 sec (run time) as shown in fig 7 (a).

The reference speed is kept constant at 1000 RPM the output speed of PID reaches 450 RPM (90% of reference value) at a time of 1.08 sec (rise time), its maximum overshoot is 9.47% and the response settles at a time of 4.45 sec (settling time). After 7 sec a load

TL1 with initial value of 0 and final value of 0.01 is applied, due to which there is a sudden drop by 14.8% and it settles at a time of 4.45 sec(settling time).After 14 sec a TL2 of initial and final value of 0 and -0.01 respectively is added along with TL1 due to which there is a drop by 14.7% and it settles at a time of 4.45 sec (settling time) and the response ends at a time of 20 sec(run time) as shown in fig 7 (b).

The reference speed is kept constant at 1000 RPM the output speed of FLC reaches 450 RPM (90% of reference value)at a time of 0.25 sec(rise time),its maximum overshoot is 3.5% and the response settles at a time of 0.61 sec(settling time).After 7 sec a load TL1 with initial value of 0 and final value of 0.01 is applied, due to which there is a sudden drop by 8.7% and it settles at a time of 0.44 sec(settling time).After 14 sec a TL2 of initial and final value of 0 and -0.01 respectively is added along with TL1 due to which there is a drop by 11.7% and it settles at a time of 4.45 sec (settling time) and the response ends at a time of 20 sec(run time) as shown in fig 7 (b).

Table 4. Variation of load of a DC motor at constant speed of 500 & 1000 RPM

LOAD	PARAMETERS MEASURED	SPEED 500 RPM		SPEED 1000 RPM	
		PID	FLC	PID	FLC
INITIAL	overshoot	1.08	0.22	1.08	0.25
	time				
	settling time	4.31	0.45	4.45	0.61
	maximum overshoot & drop	9.4% overshoot	9.6% overshoot	9.47% overshoot	3.5% overshoot
LOAD AT 7 SECONDS	settling time	4.45	0.4	4.45	0.44
	maximum overshoot & drop	30% drop	11.61% drop	14.8% drop	8.7% drop
LOAD AT 14 SECONDS	settling time	4.45	0.4	4.45	0.4
	maximum overshoot & drop	29.6% overshoot	19.8% drop	14.7% overshoot	11.7% drop

From the comparison made from table 4 it is observed that the overshoot time, settling time are lesser for FLC than that for PID it is also found that the drop due to application of load is less in FLC to that of PID. This implies that the FLC responds quickly to the variations in the system and FLC response better to varying loads as shown in table 4.

5.2 Real-time Simulation observations and inference

PID RESPONSE FOR ARDUINO DUE BOARD

Fig 8

(a). Varying speed keeping the load constant at no-load (b). Varying speed keeping the load constant at full-load

Fig 8 (c).

Varying load at constant speed of 500 RPM (d). Varying load at constant speed of 1000 RPM

FLC RESPONSE FOR ARDUINO DUE BOARD

Fig 9 (a). Varying speed keeping the load constant at no-load 9 (b). Varying speed keeping the load constant at full-load

Fig 9
 (c). Varying load at constant speed of 500 RPM (d). Varying load at constant speed of 1000 RPM

PID RESPONSE FOR C2000 DELFINO F28377S BOARD

Fig 10
 (a). Varying speed at constant load at no-load 10 (b). Varying load at constant speed of 1500

FLC RESPONSE FOR C2000 DELFINO F28377S BOARD

Fig 11
 11(a). Varying speed at constant load at no-load 11 (b). Varying load at constant speed of 1500

From the results (shown in Fig 8, 9) of Real-time simulation, the real time simulation of Arduino DUE board and the Real-time simulation of C2000 Delfino F28377S (shown in Fig 10, 11) differs from the off-line simulation in that there is distortion in the observed output and it also has a better transient response. The non-linearity in response of DC motor due to the magnetic saturations can also be studied accurately from the Real time simulation. The system simulated not only runs for the run time but runs for real-time clock time thus the variation of system parameters is studied with high reliability.

6 CONCLUSION

From the results obtained and observations made it is inferred that the Fuzzy controllers have a small rise time, settling time, minimum overshoot and minimum drop under load when compared to PID this implies that the fuzzy can respond well to dynamic system conditions. It is also seen that there is a error (when compared with the reference) in case of fuzzy as only 7 fuzzy rules are used the error is more when full-load is applied at 1500 RPM this error can be considerably reduced when the number of rules that govern the fuzzy are increased which in turn increase the computation time for fuzzy controller. From the real time simulation the controller uncertainties like distortion, non-linearity due to magnetic saturation can be realized as it is based on real-time clock time rather than sample time. Hence either of controllers PID or fuzzy can be selected based on the DC requirement of a particular application and costs, but Real time simulation should be done in order to obtain the perfect tuning and rule base for PID and FLC controllers, and fuzzy is found to have a better real-time response when compared to PID.

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